

Empowering Open Science

ACCESS A VALUABLE RESOURCE OF KNOWLEDGE AND TOOLS THROUGH OUR COMPREHENSIVE TRAINING AND STRONG NETWORK OF COMPETENCE CENTRES

www.skills4eosc.eu

Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Registry & Competence Centre Network

Competence Centers are pivotal for advancing expertise in specific domains like Open Science and FAIR data. They serve as central hubs, offering resources, training, and best practices. For prospective centers, joining this network provides recognition, collaboration opportunities, and amplifies their impact within the expert community.

Setting up a Competence Centre

Join a CCs Network

Project Partners

The Skills4EOSC consortium comprises a diverse group of 44 organizations from 18 Member States and Associated Countries, including universities, research institutions, and national and regional bodies.

This fact sheet provides a comprehensive overview of the Skills4EOSC project, its objectives, and its expected impact on the Open Science landscape.

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Skills4EOSC Training Courses

Info & How to Register

Skills4EOSC provides a comprehensive training program for researchers, data stewards, and stakeholders to navigate Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Utilizing a Train-the-Trainer model, certified trainers are recognized as Master Trainers, ensuring consistent, high-quality training delivery.

General Courses

Science4Policy

Open Science Ready Institutions

Thematic Open Science

Skills4EOSC Publications

Skills4EOSC Zenodo community

Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science.

ELEVATE OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS!

Through a unified training ecosystem a pan-european initiative to cultivate open and FAIR science skills for researchers and professionals.

Addressing Critical Gaps in Open Science Competencies

Skills4EOSC directly tackles the three key gaps identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA):

1° FILLING THE OPEN SCIENCE AND DATA EXPERTISE GAP

By developing harmonized curricula and integrating Open Science essentials into academic programs, Skills4EOSC is helping build a strong foundation of Open Science knowledge.

2° DEFINING DATA PROFESSIONAL PROFILES AND CAREER PATHS

The project is mapping career profiles and defining Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) to provide clear pathways for Open Science professionals.

3° OVERCOMING FRAGMENTATION IN TRAINING RESOURCES

Skills4EOSC is creating a FAIR-by-Design methodology for learning materials and establishing a network of Competence Centres to foster collaboration and resource sharing.

Open Science Competency Development

OS Gaps	Key outcomes	Researchers	Research Support Staff	Trainers & Educators	Policymakers & Funders	Infrastructure Providers
1° Filling the Open Science & Data Expertise Gap	Harmonized Curricula and Learning Paths <i>Developing standardized Open Science (OS) training for researchers, data professionals, and policymakers across Europe.</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	
	Train-the-Trainers (TtT) Courses <i>Scaling up the number of qualified OS trainers through effective training programs.</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	
	Open Science 4 Policy Courses <i>Delivering specialized training for researchers, policymakers, and civil servants to promote the use of OS in evidence-based policy.</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	
2° Defining Data Professional Profiles and Career Paths	Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) <i>Defining clear competence requirements for various Open Science roles to foster professional recognition.</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Professional Networks <i>Building communities for data stewards, researchers, and other professionals to support continuous learning and exchange of best practices.</i>	✓	✓	✓		✓
3° Overcoming Fragmentation in Training Resources	Competence Centre Network <i>Establishing a coordinated network of national, regional, and thematic Competence Centres to provide support and harmonize training efforts.</i>	✓	✓	✓		✓
	FAIR-by-Design Methodology <i>Ensuring that training resources are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), maximizing their impact.</i>	✓	✓	✓		✓